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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE EFFICACY OF RENAL
ULTRASONOGRAPHY IN CHILDREN WITH URINARY TRACT
INFECTION**

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Abstract:

Aim: The aim of the study was to evaluate the ultrasound of the kidneys in children and adolescents admitted with uncomplicated urinary tract infections.

Patients and Methods: This retrospective study was conducted at the Pediatric Unit-I and Radiology department of Nishtar Hospital Multan for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020. Cases with a positive urine culture were included in the study. Positive urine culture was defined as 100,000 CFU / mL in the midstream or urine bag sample, or 10,000 CFU / mL in the suprapubic sample. Gender, age, ultrasound results, VCUG and DMSA scan results were recorded. For comparison, the T test, chi-square and ANOVA were used. SPSS version 18.0 (SPSS Inc, Chicago, II, USA) was used for the analysis.

Results: Our study included 625 cases. Hydronephrosis (56.40%); bladder wall thickness 33 (23.57%); hydroureter 13 (9.29%); The most common symptoms were parenchyma echogenicity 8 (5.71%) and calculus 6 (4.29%). Of 538 renal ultrasound scans, 398 (73.97%) were normal and 140 were abnormal (26.03%) ($p < 0.0001$). The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative RUS predictive value for VUR were 42.68%, 78.96%, 38.04%, and 81.99%, respectively.

Conclusion: In cases with UTI, the majority of kidney ultrasound results were normal. Hydronephrosis was the most frequently reported abnormality among VUR cases.

Key words: ultrasonography, urinary tract infection, urethral bladder drainage, VUR

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INTRODUCTION:

Urinary tract infections are common in young children with an overall incidence of 0.7% in children with a fever. Kidney ultrasound examination is recommended to detect abnormalities in the upper urinary tract in daily practice. Its non-invasive nature and low radiation make it an ideal pre-assessment tool. However, recent publications question the importance of routine renal ultrasound (RUS) in treating children with uncomplicated urinary tract infections (UTIs). The aim of the study was to evaluate kidney ultrasound, which is routinely performed in our hospital in children and adolescents with uncomplicated urinary tract infections.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This retrospective study was conducted at the Pediatric Unit-I and Radiology department of Nishtar

Hospital Multan for one-year duration from June 2019 to June 2020. Cases with a positive urine culture were included in the study. Positive urine culture was defined as 100,000 CFU / mL in the midstream or urine bag sample, or 10,000 CFU / mL in the suprapubic sample. Gender, age, ultrasound results, VCUG and DMSA scan results were recorded. For comparison, the T test, chi-square and ANOVA were used. SPSS version 18.0 (SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL, USA) was used for the analysis.

RESULTS:

Of 887 (male = 378, female = 487) cases with a primary diagnosis of UTI, urine culture was positive in 625 cases. Of the 625 cases admitted to UTIs, 487 (77.92%) were female and 138 (22.08%) were male ($p < 5$ years, hydronephrosis is the most common abnormality) (Table1).

TABLE 1: Age distribution among children admitted with urinary tract infection

Age	Number	Percentage
Newborn	20	03.20
<1yr	24	38.72
1-2yr	130	20.80
2-5 yr	126	20.16
5-10	93	14.88
>10	14	02.24

In older children, bladder wall thickening was the most common abnormality (Table 2).

TABLE 2: Ultrasound findings among children < 5 yr and children > 5 yr

Age	Hydroureter (%)	Hydronephrosis (%)	Stone (%)	Bladder wall thickness (%)	Ectopic kidney (%)	Increased parenchymal echogenicity (%)	Other (%)	Total
<5yr	10(10.0)	49(49.0)	6(6.0)	11(11.0)	6(6.0)	8(8.0)	10(10.0)	100
>5yr	03(07.5)	07(17.5)	0	22(55.0)	2(5.0)	4(10.0)	2(5.0)	40

There was a significant correlation between abnormal renal ultrasound and VUR (Table 3).

TABLE 3: Vesicourethral reflux among cases with normal or abnormal sonography

Renal ultrasound	Reflux (+)	Reflux (-)	Total
Normal	47(18%)	214(82%)	261
Abnormal*	35(38%)	57(62%)	92
Hydroureter	03	03	
Hydronephrosis	19	22	
Stone	02	02	
Bladder thickness	04	17	
Ectopic kidney	01	04	
Parenchymal echogenicity	04	05	
Other	20	04	

Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value of RUS for VUR were 42.68%, 78, 96%, 38.04% and 81.99%. It is a more common ultrasound finding in cases with VUR. There was no significant correlation between abnormal renal ultrasound and VUR results ($P = 0.432$). In men, 71 (58.7%) had normal ultrasound of

the kidneys, and 50 (41.3%) had abnormal ultrasound. In girls, 327 (78.4%) had normal ultrasound results, and 90 (21.6%) had abnormal results. Abnormal results were more common in men than in women ($P < 0.001$). Hydronephrosis was the most common abnormality detected on ultrasound in both men and women (Table 4).

TABLE 4: Distribution of ultrasound findings among males and females

	Male (%)	Female (%)
Hydronephrosis	24(48.0)	32(35.55)
Bladder wall thickening	11(22.0)	22(24.44)
Hydroureter	08(16.0)	5(5.55)
Increased parenchymal echogenicity	02(4.0)	10(11.11)
Ectopic kidney		08(8.90)
Renal stone	01(2.0)	05(5.55)
Other	04(8.0)	08(8.90)
Total	50(100.0)	90(100.0)

There was no significant in the case of circumcision and non-circumcision with respect to the results of the ultrasound. Of the circumcised boys, 24 (68.6%) had *E. coli* in their urine cultures and 61 (70.9%) were *E. coli* negative ($P = 0.797$). In five (26.3%) cases of circumcised boys and 17 (30.9%) of uncircumcised boys, neuromuscular reflux occurred ($P = 0.706$). Of the 625 urine cultures, *E. coli* (83.3%) was the most common pathogen, followed by *Klebsiella pneumonia* (9%); *Proteus* (2.8%); *Enterobacter* (1.5%); and *Coagulase Negative Staph*

(1.2%). Of 434 cases with positive *E. Coli* UTI, 103 (23.73%) had abnormal ultrasound images, and 331 (76.27%) had normal kidney ultrasound. In 81 cases with other bacteria, 24 (29.62%) cases had an abnormal ultrasound scan and 57 (70.37%) had a normal US scan. There was no significant difference between *E. coli* positive and other bacteria in terms of abnormal ultrasound ($P = 0.2$). In both *E. Coli* and Non-*E. coli*, normal ultrasound was significantly higher than abnormal ultrasound ($p < 0.001$).

TABLE 5: Result of Renal Ultrasound among Circumcised and Non-Circumcised boy

Circumscion	Normal Sonography	Abnormal sonography
Yes	20(55.6)	16(44.4)
No	51(60.0)	34(40.0)

DISCUSSION:

In the present study, the most common age of infection was <12 months. This finding was similar to the study by Wagenlehner *et al*. But our results were inconsistent with the studies by Yuksel *et al*. In our study, 77.92% of the cases were girls. In the study by Zamir *et al*. Girls accounted for 75.3% of cases⁸. In Hoberman *et al*. In the study, 89.32% of cases were girls. The result of our study was similar to this study with a slight difference in the age of the cases. The main causative factors in our study were *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Proteus*

sp. Our discovery was similar to Zamira *et al*. Study. In a study from Saudi Arabia including 130 patients with UTI, 92 (69.7%) had normal kidney ultrasound and 38 (30.3%) had normal kidney ultrasound. In their study, of 38 cases with abnormal kidney ultrasound, 50% had VUR on VCUG. In our study, of 92 cases with abnormal ultrasound, 38% had VUR on VCUG. The results of the two studies showed little difference, but our study included a larger sample (625 cases) compared to the study by Alshamsan *et al*. With 130 cases. In a prospective study by Hoberman *et al*. On 309 children aged 1-24

months, the results of kidney ultrasound were normal in 88% (272 out of 309) of cases. In 37 cases, 41 irregularities were found. Most of the abnormalities were related to pelvic dilation (13 cases), lesser pelvis (12 cases), ureter dilation (9 cases) and hydronephrosis (2 cases). In a study by Montini et al. 300 children with 1st febrile UTI, kidney ultrasound was abnormal in 13% (38 out of 300) of cases. In a study from Finland on 399 ultrasound of the kidneys, 31 boys and 40 girls had abnormal results. Zamir et al., In a 255 ultrasound of the kidneys, 85.8% were normal. In their study, of 219 cases with normal ultrasound, 38 patients had abnormal VCUG. DiPietro et al. Studied 70 children aged <5 years using both VCUG and RUS. Five children had abnormal kidney ultrasound and 65 had normal RUS. In the Smelli-Rigden study of 58 children with UTI, VCUG VUR was found in 62% of cases, but only 8 cases had abnormal RUS. They concluded that RUS is an unreliable method of detecting VUR. In our study, hydronephrosis was the most common symptom among VUR cases. A similar result was obtained by Alshamsan et al. In the study by Montini et al., The authors concluded that the benefits of ultrasound in the acute phase of the disease were minimal. In a study in Saudi Arabia, ultrasound has little value in treating a child with their first UTI with a fever. Hoberman et al. Concluded that the ultrasound of the kidneys is of little value in the treatment of children with urinary tract infection. As noted in most studies, kidney ultrasound was normal in most UTI cases.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the kidney ultrasound was normal. Ultrasound is of little value in treating a child with an uncomplicated urinary tract infection. Hydronephrosis was the most common abnormality among VUR cases. A follow-up investigation is recommended to determine the role of renal ultrasound in treating urinary tract infections.

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